

Yield Analysis of Interfaces

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This paper deals with the problem of yield analysis of interfaces, *i.e.*, the determination of the ultimate load which can be carried by a thin interphase existing between two different bodies. We use the asymptotic expansion method and we compare this approach with the others commonly used in the study of the plasticization of interfaces (see, for example, [1]).

We present a general theory which permits calculating the limit load in a simplified model where the interface is treated as a geometrical surface with its own strength resistance. This theory can be applied to several fields of engineering, such as geotechnique (sliding of faults), adhesives, applied mechanics, etc., and it finds a natural application in the study of composites. For example, it is well known that the properties of the interface between fiber and matrix play a determinant role in the strength resistance of fiber-reinforced composites. More generally, a detailed analysis of how the interface properties influence the characteristic of the entire body is required. In the framework of linearized elasticity, this study has been done by several author and we cite, among others, [2], [3], while the problem of damaged and plastic interface is considered by Ganghoffer *et al.* [4]. These investigations are extended to the yield analysis in this work.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Let us consider three bodies Ω^+ , Ω^- and Ω^m as in Fig. 1. An example which comes from civil engineering is that of steel and concrete composite beams with shear connectors (Fig. 2). We suppose that the two main bodies Ω^+ and Ω^- are joined along their common boundary by an interphase made of a third material which fills the domain $\Omega^m = \epsilon d \times S$ and which has a small thickness. To simplify the analysis, we have assumed that S is flat and that it belongs to the plane (x_1, x_2) , although this hypothesis can be relaxed without difficulties.

Let us suppose that a nominal distribution of body forces \mathbf{f} and of boundary stresses \mathbf{g} is given. The problem of yield analysis is that of finding the maximum value of the multiplier of loads λ such that $\lambda \mathbf{f}$ and $\lambda \mathbf{g}$ can be equilibrated by an admissible field of stresses $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$, *i.e.*, a field which satisfied in each point the condition $\boldsymbol{\sigma} \in P$, where P is a convex set in the space of symmetric tensors which contains all the admissible stress. Although classical expressions of P are given by the Huber-Hencky-Von Mises criterion, by the Tresca criterion, by the Coulomb criterion, and so on, we do not make any restrictive hypothesis and we only require that P is a convex set containing the origin.

The mathematical formulation of the yield analysis problem is [5]:

(p) find $\lambda_s^e = \sup\{ \lambda \text{ such that there exists } \boldsymbol{\sigma}: \Omega \rightarrow \text{Sym} \text{ such that:}$

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{div} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^+ + \mathbf{f}^+ &= 0, \text{ in } \Omega^+, & \boldsymbol{\sigma}^+ \mathbf{n} &= \mathbf{g}^+, \text{ in } {}^s \Gamma^+, & \boldsymbol{\sigma}^+ \mathbf{e}_3 &= \boldsymbol{\sigma}^m \mathbf{e}_3, \text{ in } S^+, \\ \operatorname{div} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^m + \mathbf{f}^m &= 0, \text{ in } \Omega^m, & \boldsymbol{\sigma}^m \mathbf{n} &= \mathbf{g}^m, \text{ in } {}^s \Gamma^m, & \boldsymbol{\sigma}^m \mathbf{e}_3 &= \boldsymbol{\sigma}^- \mathbf{e}_3, \text{ in } S^-, \\ \operatorname{div} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^- + \mathbf{f}^- &= 0, \text{ in } \Omega^-, & \boldsymbol{\sigma}^- \mathbf{n} &= \mathbf{g}^-, \text{ in } {}^s \Gamma^-, \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}^+ &\in P(\Omega^+), \boldsymbol{\sigma}^+ \mathbf{e}_3 &\in P(S^+), \boldsymbol{\sigma}^m &\in P(\Omega^m), \boldsymbol{\sigma}^- \mathbf{e}_3 &\in P(S^-), \boldsymbol{\sigma}^- &\in P(\Omega^-) \}. \end{aligned}$$

In the previous expression ${}^s \Gamma$ is the part of the boundary subjected to applied external stresses $\lambda \mathbf{g}$ and ${}^u \Gamma$ is the complementary part of the boundary which is constrained to have null displacements. The

superscripts +, - and m means that the related quantity corresponds to Ω^+ , Ω^- and Ω^m , respectively. Finally, the conditions $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^\pm \mathbf{e}_3 \in P(S^\pm)$ means that we admit the possibility of the plasticization of the junction between the adherents and the adhesive (subinterfacial sliding). Thus, the discontinuity of the displacements between the adherents can be a consequence of two distinct mechanisms: the plasticization of the boundary layer of the interface, and the plasticization of the adhesive. This formulation permits, for example, to take into account for frictional constraints.

The problem (p) is usually difficult to solve, since there are many mathematical constraints in the maximization problem and because the small thickness εd of the interphase produces serious problems in the numerical solution. Thus, it may be useful to develop approximate formulations of the problem (p) which reduces the number of mathematical constraints and which permits to avoid the numerical problems due to the thinness of Ω^m . The aim of the present work is to show that, under suitable hypothesis, if ε is sufficiently small, the problem (p) can be approximated by the more simple problem

$$(p_0) \text{ find } l_s = \sup \{ \lambda \text{ such that there exists } \boldsymbol{\sigma}: \Omega \rightarrow \text{Sym} \text{ such that:}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{div} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^+ + \mathbf{f}^+ &= 0, \text{ in } \Omega^+, & \boldsymbol{\sigma}^+ \mathbf{n} &= l \mathbf{g}^+, \text{ in } {}^s \Gamma^+, \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}^+ \mathbf{e}_3 &= \boldsymbol{\sigma}^- \mathbf{e}_3, \text{ in } S, \\ \operatorname{div} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^- + \mathbf{f}^- &= 0, \text{ in } \Omega^-, & \boldsymbol{\sigma}^- \mathbf{n} &= l \mathbf{g}^-, \text{ in } {}^s \Gamma^-, \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}^+ \in P(\Omega^+), \boldsymbol{\sigma}^+ \mathbf{e}_3 &\in P(S), \boldsymbol{\sigma}^- \in P(\Omega^-) \end{aligned} \}.$$

where $P(S) = P(S^+) \cap \bar{P}(\Omega^m) \cap P(S^-)$ and where $\bar{P}(\Omega^m)$ is defined by the condition

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_{13} \\ S_{23} \\ S_{33} \end{bmatrix} \in \bar{P}(\Omega^m) \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & S_{13} \\ 0 & 0 & S_{23} \\ S_{13} & S_{23} & S_{33} \end{bmatrix} \in P(\Omega^m).$$

In the case of isotropic convex which can be expressed in the form $f(S_1, S_2, S_3) \leq k$, where $S_1 \leq S_2 \leq S_3$ are the principal tensions, the previous relation can be expressed in the form $f[0.5(S_{33} - \sqrt{S_{33}^2 + 4t^2}), 0, 0.5(S_{33} + \sqrt{S_{33}^2 + 4t^2})] \leq k$, where $t^2 = S_{13}^2 + S_{23}^2$. For example, the Rankine, the Tresca and the Huber-Hencky-Von Mises criteria become, respectively, $|S_{33}| + \sqrt{S_{33}^2 + 4t^2} \leq k$, $\sqrt{S_{33}^2 + 4t^2} \leq k$, and $\sqrt{S_{33}^2 + 3t^2} \leq k$.

Problem (p_0) is the searched simplification of the actual problem (p). One of the main advantage is that the interphase material disappears from a geometrical point of view, although its strength resistance is taken into account in the definition of $P(S)$. We also present the dual (kinematical) formulation of problem (p) and we show that, when ε tends to zero this problem tends, at least formally, to the dual problem of (p_0).

References

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